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**IMPROVED MATHEMATICAL IMPLEMENTATION OF SYMMETRIC
AND ASYMMETRIC ENCRYPTION ALGORITHMS**

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Annotation: Currently, the cryptographic algorithms are not sufficiently studied. Thus, a threat to information security remains an urgent issue. A perfect mathematical and software implementation of these algorithms is not available. Therefore, in this thesis, improved mathematical and software implementation of symmetric and asymmetric encryption algorithms are mentioned.

Keywords: RSA Algorithm, Encryption, Decryption, Cryptosystem, Security, Public Key, Private Key.

Security refers to the process of keeping information confidential by protecting it from unauthorized users. According to security goal, confidentiality means to keep a data secured. It must be hidden from unauthorized access. Integrity proposes prevention of modifications. Availability means data being available to authorized persons when needed the data. Confidentiality, integrity, and availability are three security goals [1,2]. Security goal can achieve using cryptography which is a widely used method around the world.

Cryptography is a Greek word which means secret writing. It ensures secure communication and prevents the public from reading private messages. The cryptographic system is usually characterized by three main dimensions. They are, the operations involved in the transformation of plain text to cipher text, the number of secret keys used and the method of processing the plaintext [2].

RSA is known for such type of algorithm [3]. It takes two large prime number “p” and “q” and multiplies them to get a big number “N”. The idea behind RSA is some mathematical operation easier to do but the inverse is very difficult without any additional information.

This paper presents a new modification of RSA algorithm which is Modified RSA (MRSA) based on “n” distinct prime numbers with double encryption and decryption process. The weakness of RSA algorithm is the use of two prime numbers, small encryption exponent and use the same key for encryption and signing. This schema is based on “n” distinct prime numbers instead of two prime numbers which give an opportunity to select a big encryption exponent from large product “N” to enhance the security. Numerous prime numbers and big encryption exponent increase the factoring time comparing to RSA algorithm. The double encryption and decryption process make the algorithm stronger than RSA.

Modified RSA algorithm

The proposed Modified RSA (MRSA) scheme focuses on mitigating the major issues of RSA system. Most cases the major issue is, it is breakable because of easily computation of keys based on “N”. Since it is the only product of two prime numbers, “N” can be easily traceable. Once the “N” is obtained, a hacker can find the keys and break the system. The proposed model involves value of “n” distinct prime numbers. In this thesis, all calculation and performance analysis is performed using four large prime numbers. The public and private key exponent consists of three components. “N” is the product of four prime numbers “w”, “x”, “y”, and “z”. The public key exponent consists of three components (e, f, N) where “e” and “f” are randomly taken. It further adds more complexity along with the factoring of “N”. Since only the value of “N” is kept as a public and private component, an attacker with the knowledge of “N” cannot determine the value of four prime numbers which are the basis for finding the value of “N” and subsequently “e” and “f”. The private key exponent consists of three components (d, g, N). For security purpose, the bit length of all four-chosen prime is of the same length as in case of traditional RSA.

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